

Terpenoids and Related Compounds :
Part XX¹. Careaborin, A New Triterpene
Ester from the Leaves of *Careya arborea*

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CAREYA *arborea* Roxb.², a common tree growing in West Bengal, belongs to the family Lecythidaceae. The bark of this plant is extensively used as an antipyretic³. Previous workers reported the isolation of cardiac glycosides^{4,5}, several triterpenes⁶ and velonic acid dilactone⁷ from this plant. The present reinvestigation on the leaves of this plant led to the isolation of a new triterpene ester, designated careaborin(I) and shown to have the taraxeryl *p*-hydroxy-*trans*-cinnamate structure, in addition to β -amyrin and ellagic acid-4,4'-dimethyl ether(VII).

(M^+614), $[\alpha]_D + 13.3^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.06); ν_{max} (KBr) 1785 cm^{-1} (phenolic acetate), 1245 cm^{-1} . The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum (CDCl_3 , 80 MHz, δ) of II showed a sharp singlet at 2.26 (3H) for the acetoxy methyl ($-\text{OCOCH}_3$), and a pair of 1H doublets centered at 7.60 and at 6.33 ($J=16\text{Hz}$) characteristic of *trans*-olefinic protons of cinnamoyl moiety; the more downfield doublet is assignable to the proton at the β -position to the carbonyl group. Careaborin acetate(II) also showed signals at 6.89 (2H, *d*, $J=8\text{Hz}$) and 7.33 (2H, *d*, $J=8\text{Hz}$) attributable to the two *ortho* hydrogens and the two *meta* hydrogens respectively with respect to the acetate group. A double doublet centered at 5.50 (1H, $J=4\text{Hz}$ and 8Hz) is assigned to the vinylic proton at C-15 of the taraxerane skeleton⁹. The axial methine proton at C-3 appeared as a double doublet centered at 4.60 ($J=5\text{Hz}$ and 9Hz). In addition, signals at 1.10 (3H, *s*), 0.97 (6H, *s*), 0.95 (6H, *s*), 0.90 (6H, *s*) and 0.82 (3H, *s*) indicated the presence of eight tertiary methyls.

The mass spectrum of careaborin showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 572 in conformity with its molecular formula $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_8$. The fragmentation

The ethanol extract of the powdered defatted leaves (800 g) of *Careya arborea* was washed with ether several times. The combined ether washings on evaporation gave a residue (5 g) which upon chromatography over silica gel afforded from the CHCl_3 -MeOH (95 : 5) eluates careaborin(I), crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture in pale yellow globules (yield : 0.005%), m.p. 257-58°, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_8$ ($M^+ 572$); positive Liebermann-Burchard test (triterpene); yellow colouration with TNM ($>\text{C}=\text{C}<$); violet colour with FeCl_3 (phenolic OH); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$), 1700 (ester), 1660, 1595, 1500 (aromatic); λ_{max} (EtOH) 313 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.56) which shifted to 368 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.60) in alkali, reminiscent of *p*-hydroxy-cinnamoyl moiety⁸. On treatment with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$, careaborin afforded an acetate(II), crystallised from CHCl_3 -petrol as greyish white needles, m.p. 160°; $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_8$

pattern¹⁰ strongly indicated the structure of careaborin as taraxeryl *p*-hydroxy-*trans*-cinnamate. The occurrence of peaks at m/e 572 (26.4), 448 (23.6), 393 (7.2), 284 (13.6), 269 (15.7), 204 (64.3), 189 (15.7), 147 (100%) corroborated such a conclusion.

The structure of careaborin was finally settled by hydrolysing it in 2% methanolic KOH to afford taraxerol(III). The latter was crystallised from petrol-chloroform as needles, m.p. 277-78°, $[\alpha]_D + 5^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.0386), $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$ ($M^+ 426$); ν_{max} (KBr) 3510 ($-\text{OH}$), 1640 ($>\text{C}=\text{C}<$), 1460, 1370; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 80 MHz, δ): 5.52 (1H, *dd*, $J=4\text{Hz}$ and 11.2Hz, H-15), 3.19 (1H, *dd*, $J=5\text{Hz}$ and 8Hz, H-3 α), 2.03 (1H, *dd*, $J=4\text{Hz}$ and 11.2 Hz, H-16), 1.78 (1H, *dd*, $J=4\text{Hz}$ and 11.2 Hz, H-16), 1.10, 0.99, 0.96, 0.92, 0.83, 0.82 (each 3H, *s*) and 0.94 (6H, *s*) accounting for the eight tertiary methyl groups; acetate(IV) ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$) m.p. 298-300°, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_8$

(M^+ 468); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1735, 1260. The other hydrolysis product was identified as *p*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid (or *p*-coumaric acid)¹¹ isolated as its methyl ester from CHCl_3 -petrol as needles, m.p. 90°.

A greenish yellow solid was obtained from the 10% methanolic chloroform eluates of the main chromatogram which on repeated chromatographies over silica gel, furnished ellagic acid-4,4'-dimethyl ether (V), crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH in pale yellow globules (0.001%), m.p. 298-300°, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 330); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3080 cm^{-1} (br, OH), 1708 (lactone), 1595, 1565 and 1470 (aromatic); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 254 nm and 376 nm which shifted to 274 nm and 434 nm respectively in alkali. On treatment with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$ (r.t. 24 hr), (V) gave an acetate (VI) from CHCl_3 -petrol as needles, m.p. 290-92°, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 414); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1770 cm^{-1} (phenolic acetate), 1735, 1695, 1470, 1240. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum (CDCl_3 , δ) of the acetate (VI) showed three singlets: at 7.88 due to two aromatic protons at C-5 and C-5'; at 4.26 assignable to two aryloxy methyls at C-4 and C-4' and at 2.40 attributed to the two acetoxy methyls at C-3 and C-3'. The failure of (V) to give positive Greissmayer reaction¹² also suggested that its two hydroxyl groups are at C-3 and C-3'. The mass spectrum of the acetate (VI) showed ion peaks 414 (M^+ , 6.7%), 386 (5.3), 372 (13.3), 344 (20), 330 (100), 286 (6.7), 302 (5.3). The early benzene eluate fractions of the main chromatogram on evaporation afforded a greenish white solid which on further chromatography furnished β -amyrin, crystallised from chloroform-petrol as needles (15 mg), m.p. 199°, $[\alpha]_D^{+80}$; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$), m.p. 182°.

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Terpenoid Constituents of *Boehmeria platyphylla* Don. : Sodium Borohydride Reduction of 5 α -Stigmastan-3,6-dione†

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BOEHMERIA *platyphylla* Don.¹ (fam. Urticaceae) is generally a long shrub growing in the outer Himalayas upto 7,000 ft, Khasia Hills, Bangladesh, South India and Srilanka and is also distributed in Malay Island, China, Japan and Africa. Earlier works² on the basic components of the plant revealed the presence of 3,4-dimethoxy- ω -(2-piperidyl) acetophenone, cyptopleurine (a phenanthraquinolizidine alkaloid) and a *secophenanthraquinolizidine* alkaloid of undetermined structure. There is no report of previous work on the non basic constituents of this plant although several sister species have been known to elaborate a number of triterpenes³, lignans⁴, flavones⁵ and fatty acids⁶. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of 5 α -stigmastan-3, 6-dione (I) (yield 0.0035%), pomolic acid (II) (0.005%), oleanolic acid (0.0073%), lupeol (0.004%) and β -sitosterol (0.012%) from the leaves and twigs of *B. platyphylla* and study on the NaBH_4 reduction products of I. To our knowledge, the present isolation of 5 α -stigmastan-3,6-dione constitutes its second occurrence in nature, the first isolation being from the twigs of *Metasequoia glyptostroboides*⁸.

Air dried and powdered leaves and twigs of *B. platyphylla* was Soxhletted with light petrol (60-80°) and chloroform in succession for 50 hrs each. The residues obtained by concentration of the extracts under reduced pressure showed the presence of only trace amount of alkaloidal constituents which was not separated. The residue from the light petrol extract was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

The concentrate of the light petrol-benzene (1:1) eluate fractions upon several rechromatographies over silica gel afforded lupeol, crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH in colourless needles, m.p. 212°, $[\alpha]_D^{+24.4}$ (CHCl_3 , *c* 0.068); acetate, m.p. 217°, $[\alpha]_D^{+41.5}$ (CHCl_3 , *c* 0.075), its identity being confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with an authentic sample.

The early benzene eluate fractions afforded β -sitosterol crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH in flakes, m.p. 137° alone and also upon admixture with an authentic sample.

The residue obtained from the later benzene eluate fractions and benzene- CHCl_3 (1:1) eluate fractions on extensive rechromatography over silica

† Part XXI in the series Terpenoids and Related Compounds', For Part XX see B. TALAPATRA, A. BASAK and S. K. TALAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 814.